

A NONLINEAR PREDICTING METHOD FOR FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITE LAMINATES SUBJECTED TO UNIAXIAL COMPRESSIVE LOAD

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ABSTRACT: A simply and efficiently computational model for the fiber-reinforced composite laminates, including stress analysis and failure detection, is developed to predict the ultimate strengths of the composite laminates. In stress analysis, the proposed nonlinear constitutive law for a single fiber-reinforced composite layer assumes that an elastic-plastic behavior exists in normal stress of fiber and matrix and the nonlinear behavior exists in in-plane shear stress. The onset of failure for individual lamina within the laminate is detected by a mixed failure criterion. In addition, the post-damage modes of composites are also taken into account. The individual layer constitutive equations are superimposed by using the classical lamination theory to yield the global laminate response. The accuracy of the proposed model is illustrated by comparing the results of numerical simulations with experimental data available in the literature and the results predicted by other failure models.

KEY WORDS: nonlinear constitutive law, variable shear parameter, mixed failure criteria, post-damage mode.

INTRODUCTION

The use of fiber-reinforced composite materials in aerospace industry or in other applied engineering, due to lightweight and high strength, has increased rapidly in recent years. In numerous cases involving the design of composite structures, there is a need for more refined analysis that takes into account phenomena such as progressive cracking and inelastic or nonlinear deformation of the composite materials. Such analysis is usually required not only to predict the deformational response, but also to provide a method to evaluate the accurate stresses to be used in failure predictions.

Most of the advanced composite materials have organic matrices; therefore, there is a significant nonlinear stress-strain behavior present in the transverse direction of lamina and particularly in shear deformation [1]. A significant number of macro-mechanical models have been proposed to represent the constitutive relation of fiber-reinforced composite materials such as nonlinear elasticity models [2,3], plasticity models [4-8], or damage theory coupled with elasticity [9]. In addition, various failure criteria have also been proposed to predict the

onset of failure in single layer within the fiber-reinforced composite laminates. There are four types of failure criteria: (a) limit theories [10], (b) polynomial theories [11-12], (c) strain energy theories [13], and (d) direct mode determining theories [14-16]. The mechanical response of fiber-reinforced composite materials is very complicated. Since there exist the significant nonlinearity on in-plane shear behavior and the elastic-plastic behavior in fiber and matrix, this work is, therefore, focusing on: (1) developing the nonlinear constitutive model of the composite lamina in stress analysis, (2) proposing a proper failure criterion to detect the damage of lamina, and (3) choosing a proper post-damage mechanism to predict the ultimate load for various composite laminates.

In this paper, a proposed analytical model is described first. Second, a material constitutive model considering the nonlinear in-plane shear behavior and the elastic-plastic behavior of the fiber and matrix is developed. Third, a mixed failure criterion is proposed and the post-damage modes are described. Then, using the ABAQUS finite element program carries out numerical analyses for various types of fiber-reinforced composite laminates subjected to uniaxial compressive load. The results obtained by employing the different failure criteria and post-damage modes are compared with each other. Finally, numerical results for the proposed nonlinear model are compared with the available experimental data [2] and the results predicted by other failure criterion [16].

ANALYTICAL MODEL

The idealized stress-strain curves shown in different stages for the proposed nonlinear failure model is illustrated in Fig. 1. In this proposed model, there comprises three basic regimes in longitudinal (fiber) and transverse direction; namely, the elastic, plastic, and post-damage regimes. And, it comprises two basic regimes in shear behavior; namely, the nonlinear, and post-damage regimes. For the present formulation, it is assumed that bilinear stress-strain curves in the principal material directions (1-direction and 2-direction) and a nonlinear stress-strain curve in pure shear condition can adequately represent the material response. During the nonlinear stage in shear behavior, the nonlinear shear modulus is depending on the shear strain. In the pre-damage regime, the elastic modulus is denoted by E_{ie} ($i = 1, 2$), the subscript “e” representing the elastic stage, in the principal material directions, and the plastic modulus is denoted by E_{ip} ($i = 1, 2$), the subscript “p” representing the plastic stage, in the principal material directions. In this stage, the model does not take into account the degradation of elastic stiffness resulting from progressive micro cracking in polymeric fiber-reinforced composites. In the post-damage regime, the elastic stiffness is forced to be zero in fiber and shear, excluding in transverse direction. It is assumed that, when ultimate failure is reached in a lamina, the particular lamina unloads through a negative

tangent modulus, E_{22f} , until no load remains in the lamina in the transverse direction.

Fig. 1 Idealized stress-strain curve of the proposed nonlinear failure model: (a) for 1-direction, (b) for 2-direction, (c) for 1-2 direction

CONSTITUTIVE MODELING OF LAMINA

For fiber-composite laminate materials, each lamina can be considered as an orthotropic layer in a plane stress condition. Taking into account the elastic-plastic behavior in the fiber and transverse directions and the nonlinearity in shear behavior, the stress-strain relations for an orthotropic lamina in the material coordinates (1,2) can be written as [2]

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_{11}} & \frac{-\nu_{21}}{E_{22}} & 0 \\ \frac{-\nu_{12}}{E_{11}} & \frac{1}{E_{22}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{12}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{Bmatrix} + S_{6666} \tau_{12}^2 \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \tau_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

In this model, S_{6666} is required to account for the in-plane shear nonlinearity. It is proposed that the value of S_{6666} is a function of shear strain, which can be determined by the stress-strain curve of pure shear test data [17].

The incremental stress-strain relations for a nonlinear orthotropic lamina can be given as

follows:

$$\Delta\{\sigma'\} = [Q_1']\Delta\{\varepsilon'\} \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta\{\sigma'\} = \Delta\{\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \tau_{12}\}^T$, $\Delta\{\varepsilon'\} = \Delta\{\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \gamma_{12}\}^T$,
and

$$[Q_1'] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_{11}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{\nu_{12}E_{22}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{21}E_{11}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{E_{22}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{1/G_{12} + 3S_{6666}\tau_{12}^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

FAILURE CRITERION AND DEGRADATION OF STIFFNESS

Tsai-Wu failure criterion has a general nature, because this failure criterion contains almost all other polynomial theories as special cases. But in some cases [17], the predicting failure stresses are unreasonable due to the failure stress of fiber exceeding the strength of material. In this study, it also finds another unreasonable prediction that the failure shear stress exceeds the strength of material. In order to eliminate this unreasonable phenomenon, the limitation of maximum stresses of fiber and pure shear are added into the Tsai-Wu failure criterion to obtain a mixed failure criterion. Under the plane stress condition, the proposed mixed failure criterion is written as the following form:

$$F_1\sigma_1 + F_2\sigma_2 + F_{11}\sigma_1^2 + 2F_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2 + F_{22}\sigma_2^2 + F_{66}\tau_{12}^2 = 1 \quad (4)$$

and

$$\frac{\sigma_1}{X_{ut}} \leq 1, \quad \frac{\sigma_1}{X_{uc}} \leq 1, \quad |\tau_{12}/S| \leq 1 \quad (5)$$

where

$$F_1 = \frac{1}{X_{ut}} + \frac{1}{X_{uc}}, \quad F_{11} = \frac{1}{X_{ut}X_{uc}}, \quad F_2 = \frac{1}{Y_{ut}} + \frac{1}{Y_{uc}}, \quad F_{22} = \frac{1}{Y_{ut}Y_{uc}}, \quad F_{66} = \frac{1}{S^2}$$

The X_{ut} , Y_{ut} and X_{uc} , Y_{uc} are the lamina longitudinal and transverse ultimate strengths in tension and compression, respectively, and S is the shear strength of the lamina. Though the stress interaction term F_{12} in Eq. (4) is difficult to determine, Narayanaswami and Adelman [18] suggested that F_{12} could be set equal to zero for practical engineering applications. Therefore, $F_{12} = 0$ is used in this study.

Material degradation within the damaged area was evaluated based on the mode of failure predicted by the failure criteria. Therefore, the residual stiffness of composites greatly depends on the failure mode in each layer. The property degradation models for each layer

can be separated into three idealized types of failure mode named as brittle, ductile and degrading modes [2,5].

In this investigate, it is proposed that the post damage mode are idealized as the brittle behavior for σ_1 and τ_{12} and as the degrading behavior for σ_2 . The results predicted by proposed post-damage mode are compared with the results predicted by the other two failure modes, ductile and brittle modes, adopted in matrix normal stress with the same post-damage modes in fiber and shear stresses as the proposed ones.

The following three rules are used to determine whether the ply failure is caused by matrix fracture, shear failure, or fiber failure [19]:

(1) If a ply fails in the condition of $X' < \sigma_1 < X$ and $-S < \tau_{12} < S$, the failure is assumed to be rein induced. In this case, the constitutive matrix of the lamina becomes

$$[Q_1'] = \begin{bmatrix} E_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & E_{22f} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{12n} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where E_{22f} is a negative tangent modulus in transverse after matrix failure, and

$$G_{12n} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{G_{12}} + 3S_{6666}\tau_{12}^2}$$

The term G_{12n} denotes the nonlinear shear modulus.

(2) If the ply fails in the condition of $X_{uc} < \sigma_1 < X_{ut}$, and $\tau_{12} \geq S$ or $\tau_{12} \leq -S$, the failure is assumed to be shear induced. In this case, the constitutive matrix of the lamina becomes

$$[Q_1'] = \begin{bmatrix} E_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

(3) If the ply fails with $\sigma_1 \geq X_{ut}$ or $\sigma_1 \leq X_{uc}$, the ply failure is caused by the fiber failure and assumes the total ply ruptures. Thus, the constitutive matrix of the lamina becomes

$$[Q_1'] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

LAMINATE GOVERNING EQUATIONS

The forgoing nonlinear failure model for fiber-reinforced composite laminates can be combined with classical lamination theory to form the following incremental laminate force-strain relations:

$$\Delta\{N\} = \sum_{i=1}^n [Q]_i t_i \Delta\{\varepsilon\} \quad (9)$$

where $\Delta\{N\} = \Delta\{N_x, N_y, N_{xy}\}^T$ and $\Delta\{\varepsilon\}$ are the vectors of the incremental resultant membrane forces and the incremental strains in the overall laminate coordinate system (x, y) , respectively, t_i is the thickness of the i^{th} layer, n is the number of layers. The matrix $[Q]_i$ stands for the elastic, elastoplastic and post-damage constitutive matrices whichever is applicable.

NUMERICAL ANALYSES

The aforementioned calculation model for composite materials are implemented into a finite element code and linked to the ABAQUS program. Basically, stresses and strains are calculated at each incremental step, and evaluated by the failure criteria to determine the occurrence of failure and the mode of failure. Mechanical properties in the damage area are reduced appropriately, according to the property degradation models. Stresses and strains will then be recalculated to determine any additional damage as a result of stress redistribution at the same load. This procedure will continue until no additional damage is found, and the next increment is then pursued. The final collapse load is determined when the composite plates cannot sustain any additional load.

In order to verify the proposed analytical model, numerical results generated from the model are compared with the available test data [2]. The material properties and strengths of Boron/Epoxy composites used in the calculation are:

(1) Material properties:

$$E_{11e} = 207 \text{ GPa}, E_{11p} = 180 \text{ GPa}, E_{22e} = 21.2 \text{ GPa}, E_{22p} = 15.9 \text{ GPa}, E_{22f} = -33.116 \text{ GPa},$$

$$G_{12} = 7.25 \text{ GPa}, \nu_{12} = 0.3$$

$$S_{6666} = \begin{cases} 15.198 \text{ GPa}^{-3}, & \text{if constant} \\ 20.61 - 20. \exp(-\gamma_{12}/0.00337) \text{ GPa}^{-3}, & \text{if variable} \end{cases} \quad [17]$$

(2) Yield Strengths:

$$X_{yt} = 828 \text{ MPa}, X_{yc} = -1346 \text{ MPa}, Y_{yt} = 57.9 \text{ MPa}, Y_{yc} = -97.3 \text{ MPa}.$$

(3) Ultimate strengths:

$$X_{ut} = 1370 \text{ MPa}, X_{uc} = -2787 \text{ MPa}, Y_{ut} = 86.3 \text{ MPa}, Y_{uc} = -262 \text{ MPa}, S = 128.6 \text{ MPa}.$$

Comparisons between various post damage modes

The stress-strain behavior of a composite laminate is greatly affected by the stress-strain behavior of individual layer. But the strength of a composite laminate is greatly controlled by the post failure mode. In order to select the proper post failure mode, three idealized post failure modes, brittle, ductile and degrading, are taken into

account.

Figures 2 through 5 illustrate the distinct results between these three post damage modes for various symmetrical angle-ply and cross-ply composite laminates.

Fig. 2 Stress-strain curves for $[+20/-20]_s$ laminate predicted by various damage modes

Fig. 3 Stress-strain curves for $[+30/-30]_s$ laminate predicted by various damage modes

Obviously, the results predicted by brittle and degrading modes are better than by ductile mode for symmetrical angle-ply composite laminates. But, for cross-ply composite laminates, it appears the same prediction.

Fig. 4 Stress-strain curves for $[0/90]_s$ laminate predicted by various post damage modes

Fig. 5 Stress-strain curves for $[+15/-75]_s$ laminate predicted by various post damage modes

Comparisons between various failure criteria

The Tsai-Wu failure criterion is one of the major quadratic failure criteria and has been extensively used in the literature. But there exists some unreasonable predictions [17] for the composite laminates subjected to uniaxial tensile load. Also, the Tsai-Wu failure criterion presents some unreasonable predictions for the symmetric angle-ply composite laminates subjected to uniaxial compressive load, shown as Fig. 6. In Fig. 6, the normalized failure

stresses are defined as:

$$(\sigma_{11f})_n = \frac{\sigma_{11f}}{X_{ut}} \text{ or } (\sigma_{11f})_n = \frac{\sigma_{11f}}{|X_{uc}|} \quad (10a)$$

$$(\sigma_{22f})_n = \frac{\sigma_{22f}}{Y_{ut}} \text{ or } (\sigma_{22f})_n = \frac{\sigma_{22f}}{|Y_{uc}|} \quad (10b)$$

$$(\tau_{12f})_n = \left| \frac{\tau_{12f}}{S} \right| \quad (10c)$$

where $(\sigma_{11f})_n$, $(\sigma_{22f})_n$, and $(\tau_{12f})_n$ denote the normalized failure stresses in 1-direction, 2-direction, and 1-2 direction, respectively. And σ_{11f} , σ_{22f} , and τ_{12f} are the failure stresses in 1-direction, 2-direction, and 1-2 direction, respectively. It shows that the results predicted by Tsai-Wu criterion and Mixed criterion are almost the same. But there are some unreasonable predictions by Tsai-Wu failure criterion for θ between $45^\circ \sim 50^\circ$ since the normalized failure shear stress, $(\tau_{12f})_n$, is over 1. For θ between $45^\circ \sim 75^\circ$, the predictions of $(\sigma_{22f})_n$ are somewhat different between Edge criterion and Tsai-Wu or Mixed criterion.

Fig. 6 Normalized failure stresses predicted by various criteria

Fig. 7 and 8 illustrates the stress-strain relations predicted by Edge criterion and Mixed criterion, and compares the predictions with the test data [2]. For $[+60/-60]_s$ laminate, the failure stresses predicted by Edge and Mixed criteria are far underestimated with respect to the test data. For $[0/90]_s$ laminate, it shows that the predicted curves are in good agreement with the experimental curve, and the failure prediction by Mixed criterion is better than the prediction by Edge criterion.

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Fig. 7 Stress-strain curves for $[+60/-60]_s$ laminate predicted by various failure criteria

Fig. 8 Stress-strain curves for $[0/90]_s$ laminate predicted by various failure criteria

Fig. 9 illustrates the failure stress for various symmetric angle-ply laminates predicted by Edge criterion and Mixed criterion, and compares the predictions with the test data [2]. It shows that the predictions are in good agreement with the experimental data, excepting for $[+60/-60]_S$ laminate. Maybe the response of $[+60/-60]_S$ laminate is very complicated. It needs a more refine analysis to simulate the behavior of $[+60/-60]_S$ laminate.

Fig. 9 Failure stresses for various angle-ply laminates predicted by different criteria

CONCLUSIONS

The proposed nonlinear predicting method for composite materials includes three parts: (1) nonlinear constitutive law, (2) mixed failure criterion, and (3) post-damage mode. For nonlinear stress analysis, the constitutive law of the material contains the elastic-plastic behavior in fiber and matrix and the nonlinearity with a variable shear parameter in shear stress. In damage detection, the mixed failure criterion is used to determine the onset of damage for the composite laminate in the loading process. In the post-damage analysis, the degrading mode for matrix stress and the brittle mode for fiber stress and shear stress are taken into account to calculate the degradation of stiffness. The comparison of numerical simulations with other failure criteria and various coupon tests illustrate that the proposed nonlinear model can adequately predict the material response characteristics of fiber-reinforced composite laminates under a uniaxial compressive loading condition. The favorable agreement between the present numerical predictions and experimental results demonstrate that the proposed nonlinear failure model is a useful tool in the inelastic analysis of fiber-reinforced composite laminated material. The practical significance of the present results is that using the proper failure criterion and the adequate degradation of stiffness in each damaged ply in post-damage analyses can obtain the more exact predictions of failure stress for the composite laminates. The good agreement with experiment shows the potential of the present nonlinear failure approach.

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